

Change Management Checklist

Project: _____

Responsible: _____

Date: _____

Question	Compliance	Comments
1. Is the request a real change or a specific customization?	<input type="checkbox"/> Real Change	
2. Does the change refer to a Functional Requirement (RF) or a Non-Functional Requirement (NFR)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3. Does the change impact existing requirements (scope, deliverables, or previous versions)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
4. Is there a direct impact on the schedule, cost, or team effort?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
5. Will the change result in significant rework? If so, has it been assessed?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
6. Has a technical impact and feasibility analysis been conducted?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
7. Was the change discussed with the PO and/or Project Manager before the final decision?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
8. Was the change recorded and prioritized in the backlog once accepted?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
9. Does the change benefit more than one client or stakeholder, or bring collective value?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
10. Was there resistance to change? If so, was it discussed and justified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Template Change Request - Complete

Request ID:	
Change Requester:	Name of the person or team requesting the change
Approval Responsible:	Name of the PO, PM, or responsible stakeholder
Request Date:	Date the request was submitted
Affected System Version:	e.g., v1.2.0
Type of Change:	Bug fix, improvement, new feature, customization, other
Change Category:	FR (Functional Requirement), NFR (Non-Functional Requirement), interface, process, documentation, other
Detailed Description:	Explanation of the need and context
Change Impact	
Does it impact existing requirements?	Yes/No
Impacted or related requirements:	Indicate related FRs or NFRs
Does it impact the project scope?	Yes/No
Schedule Impact:	Describe estimated impact on timeline
Cost Impact:	Indicate if additional budget or funding is required
Team Effort Impact:	Estimated hours or additional resources needed
Technically Feasible?	Yes/No
Feasibility and Impact Analysis Notes:	Risks, dependencies, limitations, or alternative solutions evaluated
Acceptance Criteria:	How will we know the change has been implemented correctly?
Priority:	High/Medium/Low
Registered in the backlog:	Yes/No
Change Request Status:	Not started ▾

Template Change Request - Simplified

Request ID:	
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Change Requester:	Name of the person or team requesting the change
Approval Responsible:	Name of the PO, PM, or responsible stakeholder
Request Date:	Date the request was submitted
Affected System Version:	e.g., v1.2.0
Type of Change:	Bug fix, improvement, new feature, customization, other
Change Category:	FR (Functional Requirement), NFR (Non-Functional Requirement), interface, process, documentation, other
Detailed Description:	Explanation of the need and context
Change Impact:	Scope/Schedule/Cost
Does it impact existing requirements?	Yes/No
Impacted or related requirements:	Indicate related FRs or NFRs
Technically Feasible?	Yes/No
Acceptance Criteria:	How will we know the change has been implemented correctly?
Priority:	High/Medium/Low
Change Request Status:	Not started -